

Tackling water scarcity in semi-arid mediterranean regions: A Machine Learning approach for water resources forecasting in groundwater and surface water bodies

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The semi-arid regions of the Mediterranean coast, such as Western Costa del Sol (SE Spain), are characterized by frequent and long time periods of low rainfall, high temperatures and a strong dependence of groundwater. Increasing water demands (mainly due to tourism for drinking water and golf course irrigation) has caused a depletion of piezometric levels and stored water in reservoirs. In this study, funded by HEU call (MAR2PROTECT on-going project), the impact of water scarcity on groundwater status at Marbella-Estepona Groundwater Body (060.040) and surface water availability in reservoirs (La Concepción, Charco Redondo and Guadarranque) have been assessed by Machine Learning techniques. Time series of groundwater levels, electrical conductivity and stored water in reservoirs have been used as input data for AI-based predictive models. The outputs coming from these models are utilized for obtaining future values of regional water scarcity indicators based on the requirements of the corresponding Drought Management Plans. Moreover, to improve the goodness of fit of the predicted results, different Machine Learning algorithms (Linear Regression, XGboost, Random Forest...) have been tested and the target variable has been iterated with other explanatory variables (aquifer recharge, rainfall, pumping rates, ...). We have also fitted the best combination of variables to obtain high precision ($\approx 80\%$ in the coming 3 months) while maintaining a good bias-variance ratio. The use of Machine Learning models can be a very helpful tool for an efficient management of water resources in scenarios such as the one studied, where socio-economic activities are highly dependent on freshwater availability.